

DIFFERENT APPROACHES TO TEACHING ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE TO YOUNG LEARNERS

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***Abstract:** this article analysis teaching methods, learning strategies, sense-creative technologies, emotional and psychological peculiarities of English as a foreign language. Using a foreign language a teacher familiarizing younger to a different culture on the one hand and on the other hand one fosters respect and tolerance for different lifestyles.*

***Key words:** English as a foreign language, young learners, motivation, different approach, methodological concept*

In terms of language skills and fluency, pre-teens and early teens are usually quite alert and confident. They can communicate well in their own language; they are familiar with the basics of such diverse subjects as literature, history and mathematics; they are also beginning to study science as a subject, and to realize that it is a field of knowledge unlike any other. An ideal student, according to any national standards of education, has the ability and the desire to master all those skills, and to use the new information as a tool of self-development on their way to becoming a full-fledged valuable member of society.

A great many explanations have been put forward for taking into account the age, level, and goals of our students. In this section, we shall look at young beginners, and the ways to cope with their problems. Young students at the beginner level are naturally curious about all new things. Their minds and memories are uncluttered; they have no fear of the unknown. If they wish to connect with their peers, they may still be able to use non-verbal means of communication. It is interesting; children manage to play together, never feeling

any language barriers. Amazingly, they can also retell, translate into their mother tongue what the other children are saying, relay the information to adults, regardless of the language in which it was first received. At a foreign language lesson with young learners, no matter which method we use, we come across the same problem: children tend to rely on the patterns of their native tongue. On the other hand, once they learn a few words, they are ready to communicate, to talk. Poems and songs are extremely useful, as well as fairy-tales, short plays, cartoons, any and all kinds of visual aids. Have them draw simple diagrams, repeating the same forms over and over again. Children can recite the same poem, listen to the same fairy-tale, sing the same song, and watch the same cartoon hundreds of times. They will enjoy drawing the same picture and laugh at the way grammar can be learned.

Teaching techniques and EFL methodological concepts are quite different: from those based on suggestology to cognitive ones. Linguistic intelligence is revealed through specially designed grammar and vocabulary exercises based on their work in dialogues. We can distinguish two stages of working with the language material: first, the teacher presents new materials when the books are closed and then students work on it with their books opened.

The process of learning as second language, in our case English, must be similar to learning the first language, where listening goes before speaking. In this way, communicative skills are developed in a natural, spontaneous way.

However, Uzbek teachers who are used to explaining new structures before teaching pupils to communicate, in small doses, traditional Uzbek activities such as introducing phonetic transcription, drilling isolated sounds, as well as learning rules. Today, more and more attention is given to communicative approaches in EL teaching. With the emergence of universal education, and the extremely rapid development of ICT, communication became the primary goal for foreign language learners. We live in a time when information technologies play a very important role in education: their use in foreign language teaching raises motivation facilitates

students' cognitive abilities and helps to create a favorable psychological atmosphere in the classroom. This approach gives greater flexibility for language acquisition.

Teaching English to young learners has its own peculiarities based on psychophysiology of their age. Psychologists assert that preschoolers' perception, memory and attention are involuntary. Children cannot regulate their perception and analyze an object. Schoolchildren's attention is drawn by bright objects. Their concentration lasts as long as they are interested in the activity.

Learning a foreign language is a pleasant moment in a child's life. He climbs the stairs to a new level of knowledge. In an effort to teach children the basics of English phonetics, grammar and enrich their vocabulary, a teacher overshadows the individual characteristics of a child, the reaction rate, mental health. Because of this, children cannot move forward in learning knowledge as the basis for successful learning is not only the traditional age principle. Students might be very varied in their prior learning, motivation, learning style, and in other respects. One needs to teach in a way that accommodates these differences, which is called differentiation.

This study is of relevance since it sheds light on a number of issues in the current theories. The implementation of these objectives requires teachers should know the psychological characteristics of primary schoolchildren to organize the educational process at this stage of training. Today nobody is to be convinced that early language training contributes not only more durable and practical knowledge, but also carries a great intellectual, educational potential.

References

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